

A STUDY FOR ARTIFICIAL DIELECTRIC COMPOSITES BASED ON SYNTACTIC FOAM FILLED MINERAL PARTICLE

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ABSTRACT

The dielectric constant of the syntactic foam can be raised above to 2.5 by filling some mineral particle filler such as barium titanate(BaTiO_3), strontium titanate (SrTiO_3) or titanate dioxide (TiO_2) then it becomes to the high dielectric constant material. The relationship of artificial dielectric property and resin matrix type, fillers content have researched in this report.

1 INTRODUCTION

A syntactic foam is a composite material consisting of hollow glass, ceramic or resin microsphere embedded in a suitable organic resin matrix. A wide range of resin matrix is suitable and, in general, a thermosetting resin, such as epoxide, polyester phenolic or polyimide, has been used. [1,2] The density of the foam can be controlled since it is governed by the quantity of lightweight particle added to the resin. It is entirely closed cell and the ideal spherical shape of the microsphere leads to more ordered cellular structure than that obtained in low foam and hence enables the syntactic material to make a greater contribution to high strength structure components. So it is a lightweight material with good performance. [3,4,5] A conventional syntactic foam has artificially dielectric constant ranging from 1.6 to 2.5, the application of the foam has been limited because of the low constant. There are many ways for raising the dielectric constant of syntactic foam. Generally filling metal or titanate particle in the foam can artificially elevate dielectric constant above to 2.5. This is a practice method. But it has a greater loss tangent and low dielectric constant at microwave frequency. A new artificial dielectric based on syntactic foam filled mineral particle has introduced in this paper. The dielectric has greater dielectric constant and low loss tangent below 0.013. A artificial dielectric material with different dielectric constant may be made by adjusting the proportion of compositions. This is a new way of researching the

lightweight dielectrics with high dielectric constant.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Resin matrixe

- (1) high temperature epoxy resin;
- (2) diallyl phthalate resin(DAP);
- (3) bismaleimides resin(BMI);

2.1.2 Fillers

- | | |
|---------------------------------|----------------|
| (1) hollow glass microsphere | 44—125 μ m |
| (2) BaTiO ₃ particle | <50 μ m |
| (3) SrTiO ₃ particle | <50 μ m |
| (4) TiO ₂ particle | <50 μ m |

2.1.3 Toughening agent

- | | |
|---------------------|------|
| short E glass fiber | <6mm |
|---------------------|------|

2.2 Processing

The density and dielectric property of the foam material are firstly considered in order to obtain a high dielectric constant and low loss artificial dielectric material , We hope this material has high dielectric constant and low density in the same times and then other factors must be considered. Finally we obtain a satisfactory direction.

A raw material of artificial dielectric can be made through weighting every composition on proportion and mixing them. Performance of the artificial dielectric can be adusted by changing the proportion.

There are many processing of syntactic foam such as vacumm soaking , injecting or pressure moulding. Since some filler filling, the artificial dielectric must be made with new processing by testing . The authors use the new half- wetting moulding to make a artificial dielectric plate.

2.3 Testing

ASTM D2520 waveguide is used to test the dielectric constant and loss tangent at 10 GHz frequency . Instron 1185 Testing Machine is used to test the mechanics . Cambridge S—200 Scanning Electric Microscope(SEM) is used to checking inside structure. Lint 860- II X-ray Energy Dispersion Spectrocomparator(EDS) is used to analyze distribution of filler.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 resin content

The distribution of microsphere filler in the resin matrix must be considered when filling .The maxium filler content has been determined according to calculation and testing on the Maximum Packing Systems of C.C.Furnas [6] .This is the most practice method devised because it is based on the determined void volumes of specific size range of uniformly shape particle. For simplicity and comformance with sieve size .Furnas chose "one" size of range of $\sqrt{2}$. By determining the void volumes of a size range , the shape factors refered to previously are eliminated or compensated for in calculation . As succeeding finer materials is added, it occupes voids between the largest particle such total volume is not expanded. Each additional finer material also has a void volume, which, in turn, may be occupes by a still finer material. The resulting geomitric progression then depends on the least voids left in the system and very

wide ranges of particle size to achieve a high degree of packing .

In practice , one may combine different type of fillers having different particle shapes ,but not radically different. In these case, the calculations may not agree with the results obtained with the fabricated mixtures . Nonetheless, whether stepwise or continuous grading is used ,a basis is provided for predicting with a fair degree of accuracy the particle size distributions for maximum packing . Slight adjustments may be made for certain desirable properties, but the process is removed from an entirely trial and error method.

According to the stepwise grading of particles for maximum packing, the the formulations are followings :

$$S = \frac{1}{1 + V_1} + \frac{V_1}{1 + V_2} + \frac{V_1^2}{1 + V_3} + \frac{V_1^3}{1 + V_4} + \dots \quad (1)$$

$$P_f = S - SV_1^2 \quad (2)$$

$$V_v = 1 - P_f \quad (3)$$

Where S is total absolute volume of solid material, V_i is fractional voids of d_i , P_f is the volume that the solid particles occupy of the total volume, V_v is void volume.

Using the above formulations the calculation results are following:

$$P_f = 0.696$$

$$V_v = 0.304$$

Suppose the void volumes between hollow microspheres are fully filled with resin matrix, the minimum resin content may be calculated as following:

$$\text{minimum resin content } W_r = 39.5\%$$

Using mechanics properties as objective function and connecting the test, the minimum resin content is $W_r = 44\%$

3.2 Physical and mechanical properties

The physical and mechanical properties of artificial dielectric based on syntactic foam fairly depends on the resin matrix used. In past. The work on the artificial dielectric has largely concered on the use of an epoxy resin matrix.[2] However numerous additional resin such as DAP or BMI have been examined for their possible contribution in this field. The properties of artificial dielectric based on three resin matrixe are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 The properties of artificial dielectric based on different resin matrixe

No.	Resin type	Density g / cm ³	Flexure Strength (MPa)	Dielectric Constant	Loss Tangent
1	Epoxy	1.2	25	3.8	0.020
2	DAP	1.1	20	3.7	0.018
3	BMI	1.0	30	4.0	0.013

3.3 Dielectric property

Dielectric property of the artificial dielectric filled mineral particles are listed in Table 2

Table 2 Dielectric property of dielectrics filled in different particles

Filler	Density g / cm ³	Dielectric Constant	Loss Tangent
BaTiO ₃	1.2	3.63	0.06
SrTiO ₃	1.2	3.47	0.04
TiO ₂	1.0	4.0	0.013

The relationship for dielectric property and TiO₂ filler particle content is shown in Figure 1. The relationship for dielectric property and density is shown in Figure 2.

3.4 Microstructure

The artificial dielectric based on syntactic foam is a lightweight composites with high fillers. The frame of dielectric is composed with hollow microsphere and resin matrix and some mineral filler is filled inside them. The SEM and EDS photograph of the dielectric arc shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- 1.The dielectric constant of artificial dielectric based on syntactic foam can be closely controlled by the additional of the mineral fillers.
- 2.The wide range of useful matrix resin gives added versatility and makes available material with properties tailored to particular requirement.
- 3.The artificial dielectrics filled in TiO₂ mineral particle has lower loss tangent.

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Figure 1 dielectric property and TiO₂ filler content

Figure 2 dielectric property and density of artificial dielectric filled TiO₂ particle

Figure 3 artificial dielectric SEM photograph

Figure 4 artificial dielectric EDS photograph